

Crowd Funds Platform Using Blockchain Technology

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Abstract: Governments need to cater to a huge number of responsibilities of a state. The working of state governments involves huge number of transactions towards various operations that need to be carried out throughout the state. This includes new projects, repair and maintenance works, awarding contracts, paying of government employees, farmer schemes and so on. A major hurdle that the top government face is the low-level corruption that is sometimes impossible to track which deprives the state progress. Tracking it is a very difficult task due to the current system. Here we propose a smart system to track funds allocated to the state government as they travel through the government process at each stage. We here make use of blockchain technology to secure the transactions at every stage while maintaining transparency in every transaction sealing every transaction with proofs as the funds move ahead. Blockchain, originally block chain, is a growing list of records, called blocks that are linked using cryptography. Each block contains a cryptographic hash of the previous block, a timestamp, and transaction data. In this project researcher use Blockchain Algorithms for security like AES for Encryption and Decryption By design, a blockchain is resistant to modification of the data. In this paper we propose a system to track funds allocated to the government as they travel through the government process at each stage using Key pair generation algorithm, Metadata file decryption and Data verification algorithms. This system uses block-chain technology to maintain the transparency & security at every stage as the funds move ahead. This system allows us to maintain the crystal-clear record with all users who are connected in the chain to transaction the data on a need-to-know basis. The system makes use of encryption to secure transactional data using hash values to maintain a block of transactions in a chain manner, which is maintained & verified by every node involved to verify the transaction and save the data in a transparent form within the government. The system allows for a full proof, secure authentic fund allocation & fund tracking system help to form an incorruptible government procedure.

Keywords: Augmented reality, Graphical User Interface, AR virtual fitting room, Garment Model

I. INTRODUCTION

The working of governments involves huge number of transactions towards various operations that need to be carried out throughout the nation. This includes new projects, repair and maintenance works, awarding contracts, paying of government employees, farmer schemes and so on. Usually when a project is allocated funds, there is no knowledge as to how these funds are being used and a large part of it is never show in records due to corruption. To solve this problem, a system has been proposed using Blockchain to provide the transparency. A major obstacle that the top government face is the low-level corruption that is some- times not possible to track which deprives the state progress. Blockchain technology is an upcoming technology and said to be one of the most promising technologies which would revolutionize the world. Building a decentralized database infrastructure using smart contract on the Ethereum blockchain that would solve the problem of current traditional centralized database. Here we make use of blockchain technology to secure the transactions at every stage while maintaining transparency in every transaction sealing every transaction with proofs as the funds move ahead. The purpose if this project is to serve as a guide to developers and testers who are responsible for the development of the system. The transactions are the very important factor in handling financial data and tracking the funds effectively. To avoid mishandling of finance transactions must be secure and transparent and it need to be stored safely for future refences. Implementing this using blockchain will provide more convenience and protection. Input: Government Fund allotment details Technology: Blockchain Output: To create transparent fund transfer system and prevent corruption.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Software design is a stage in the software engineering process at which an executable software system is developed. It is an activity involving identification of software components based on the needs of the client. It deals with representing the client's requirement, as stated in the software requirements specification document, into a format that can be easily implemented using a programming language. The software design phase is the first step in the Software Design Life Cycle (SDLC), which shifts the focus from the problem to the solution.

Architecture Diagram: A system architecture is the conceptual model that denes the structure, behaviour, and more views of a system. An architecture description is a formal description and representation of a system, organized in a way that supports reasoning about the structures and behaviours of the system. A system architecture can consist of system components and the sub-systems developed, that will work together to implement the overall system. There have been

efforts to formalize languages to describe system architecture, collectively these are called architecture description languages (ADLs).

Figure .1 Architecture Diagram

Data Flow Diagram A Data flow diagram or DFD is a method is representing the flow of any data of a particular system or process. It also provides the information regarding the inputs and outputs of every single object and the process itself, as shown in Fig 3.2.1 The DFD is considered to be an abstract structure in creating an overview of the system without elaborating the detail study of the structure. DFDs can also be for the visualisation of data processing. It is important as it shows the implementation of information given to the system as an input whose purpose is to give out the required output. The data flow diagram does not provide any information regarding the timing or the process ordering or how the process will be processing the data in either a parallel way or a sequence way. A DFD depicts the types of data that will be input to and output from the system, as well as how the data will flow through the system and where it will be kept.

Figure .2 Data Flow Diagram

Use case Diagram A Use Case is an interaction between the user and system. It ensures the goal of the users and responsibility of the system to its users. Admin, Government body and the guest are the three users interacting with the system as shown in Figure 3.

Figure .3 Use Case Diagram

Class Diagram Class diagram describes the attributes and operations of a class and also the constraints imposed on the system. The class diagrams are widely used in the modelling of object-oriented systems because they are the only UML diagrams, which can be mapped directly with object-oriented languages. The diagram 4. shows the different classes and the attributes involved

Figure .4 Class Diagram

Sequence Diagram A sequence diagram or system sequence diagram shows process interactions arranged in time sequence in the field of software engineering. It depicts the processes involved and the sequence of messages exchanged between the processes needed to carry out the functionality. The diagram 3.5.1 shows the functionality and different processes that take place in the application.

Figure .4 Sequence Diagram

III. METHODOLOGY

Implementation basically deals with the implementing the design methodology into the state of working model. This is considered to be the very important stage of the project as this stage of the project aspects the system to the working procedure of the user. The developer implements all the design phase into the reality of the existing system to be used. Implementation is a process that puts the developed system into the actual use, along with the various working environment. The major task of the implementation stage is careful planning, looking through the system and various major constraint, the methodology design in such a way the changeover phase and also deals with evaluation.

Setting up Ganache: Ganache is a local development blockchain that can be used to mimic the behaviour of a public blockchain. It will allow us to deploy smart contracts, develop applications and run tests. Installing node package manager Once the local blockchain is running, we need to configure our environment for developing smart contract. Setting up

Truffle Framework This provides a suite of tools for developing Ethereum smart contracts with Solidity programming language.

Setting up Metamask Ethereum Wallet: Most web browsers do not currently connect to blockchain networks, so we should install metamask to do so. Metamask will allow us to manage our personal account when we connect to the blockchain, as well as manage our Ether funds that we use to pay for transactions. Deploy project After making the project work on the local blockchain instance without any problem we can now able to deploy the project to the real test network and see how this application works in the real world.

```
function addGovernmentBody(address acclNumber, string memory govBodyName, string memory govBodyRole) public {
    governmentBodyMapping[acclNumber].acclNumber = acclNumber;
    governmentBodyMapping[acclNumber].governmentBodyName = govBodyName;
    governmentBodyMapping[acclNumber].accountBalance=0;
    governmentBodyMapping[acclNumber].governmentBodyRole = govBodyRole;

    govBodyNameMapping[govBodyName] = acclNumber;

    emit AddedGovBody(govBodyName, acclNumber, govBodyRole);
}
```

Figure.5a Implementation of smart contract (addGovernmentBody)

```
function addFunds(uint funds, string memory title) public {
    require(!totalFunds().encodeHash(governmentBodyMapping[msg.sender].governmentBodyRole)
    == keccak256(abi.encodePacked("total")));

    totalFunds+=funds;

    governmentBodyMapping[msg.sender].accountBalance+=funds;

    emit AddedFunds(title, "Total Government Fund");
}
```

Figure.5b Implementation of smart contract(addFunds)

```
function transferFunds(uint funds, string memory projectName, string memory govBodyName, string memory title) public {
    require(
        !keccak256(abi.encodePacked(governmentBodyMapping[msg.sender].governmentBodyRole)
        == keccak256(abi.encodePacked("total"))) ||
        !keccak256(abi.encodePacked(governmentBodyMapping[msg.sender].governmentBodyRole)
        == keccak256(abi.encodePacked("total")))
    );

    address fundReceiver = govBodyNameMapping[govBodyName];

    require(keccak256(abi.encodePacked(msg.sender)) != keccak256(abi.encodePacked(govBodyNameMapping[govBodyName])));

    governmentBodyMapping[msg.sender].accountBalance-=funds;

    governmentBodyMapping[msg.sender].accountBalance+=funds;

    emit TransferFunds(funds, msg.sender, fundReceiver, governmentBodyMapping[msg.sender].governmentBodyName, governmentBodyMapping[fundReceiver].governmentBodyName);

    emit TotalBalance(governmentBodyMapping[msg.sender].accountBalance);
}
```

Figure.5c Implementation of smart contract (transferFunds)

Figure.5d Ganache Home screen

The figure 5 shows the home screen of Ganache blockchain, with 10 user accounts with 100.00 ETH in each.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Figure 6 shows the truffle migration using Git Bash. It takes few minutes to complete the migration. Figure.7 shows the steps involved in deployment of blockchain network. Once the execution is completed the local blockchain network will be running at port 3000. The figure 8 shows the home page of the web interface used for government fund allocation and tracking.

Figure.11 Login Options

Figure.12 Fund Transactions

Figure.13 User login using Metamask

Figure.14 Home Page Transaction Details

The figure 11 shows the way the fund is allocated or added to financial system of government. The figure 12 shows the transaction of funds across different government bodies. The figure 13 shows user login to metamask using the private key of the user. The figure 14 shows transaction history at homepage to all users including guest users.

IV. CONCLUSION

Blockchain decreases conflict and increases security by making it impossible to alter every block providing integrity, transparency. Cyber-Trust platform relies on advanced intrusion detection tools to identify malicious activities and enhance security. The fund transfer information is safely stored as raw data in a blockchain database, while hashes and meta data of the transactions are stored on the blockchain.

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